

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NETWORKING AS A REQUISITE FOR CAREER AND ITS IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Professionals and people in general use networking in a daily basis consciously or unconsciously. Little do they know that this could make or break their career, promotions, remuneration and even catapult them in the corporate ladder if understood properly and used.

This study will delve deep in the psychology of employees and more importantly the reflection of their beliefs in the behavior and networking style. The study is a collection and synthesis of other similar works in the classification of networking styles and their respective efficiency in the workplace.

Networking if used properly can be a powerful tool in the work-life balance and career advancement. On the other hand, it also can be a barrier and an obstacle in the path. Employees of any level, managers and C-level executives all should learn perfectly the benefits of proper networking or suffer the consequences of not knowing at the hand of their colleague-competitors.

Keywords: Networking, Career, Management, Cognitive Styles, Social Capital

Jel Classification: D23, D71, D85

Introduction

Career advancement sometimes is influenced by a twist of fate or distinguished talent. But sometimes and more often is a product of good performance with controlled and calculated moves in teams with key players that is known as networking. Networking is inevitable in workplace and is often underrated when it comes to the effect that this has on one's career and workplace harmony.

Existing studies have investigated how personality traits, such as self-monitoring (Kilduff, 2008), shape social networks. The effect of personality on types of social capital has also been studied (Sasovova et al., 2010). However, strong ties also create what are called maintenance costs, such as in terms of time spent helping others (Hansen, 2002). On the other hand, very strong ties within a group or a closed network can also slow down work. Even worse, clans will even prevent individual participants from seeking information from outside (Hansen et al. 2005). However, strong ties facilitate and encourage easy commenting and innovation among participating members.

Research to date has shown that the workplace social network within which an employee is embedded profoundly influences his or her ability to produce useful organizational innovations (Greve, & Tsai, 2004). One well-established line of research, in particular, argues that occupying a position in the network of information circulation and mediation that flows throughout the structural part of a group or organization enhances individuals' creativity (Burt, 2000). By receiving information from colleagues who are not part of the group (Aral & Alstytne, 2011), employees in such positions are more likely to find and combine diverse and seemingly unrelated information, which is critical for conceiving new approaches and creative solutions (Amabile, 1996a). In support of this argument, previous studies have found that employees with a rich workplace network with extensive scale and

structure generate more and more original ideas than comparable individuals in similar positions positioned within a closed network of interconnected contacts (Burt, 2004).

The ability to generate original, out-of-the-box ideas represents a salient and intrinsically valuable aspect of an employee's innovative performance, because such ideas are the seeds from which organizational innovations can develop (Oldham, & Cummings, 2003). Existing research from a variety of empirical settings supports the view that individuals involved in intermediary networks tend to be more innovative than equally skilled colleagues occupying closed network positions.

Cognitive style refers to "enduring individual differences in the ways people organize and process information" (Martinsen, Kaufmann, & Furham, 2011: 214), which influence how individuals conceptualize and approach problems. Cognitive style theories have become increasingly important in organizational research, as evidence suggests that cognitive styles are "a fundamental factor determining individual and organizational behavior" (Kozhevnikov, 2007). A prominent example is Kirton's Adaptation-Innovation Theory (Kirton, 1976, 1989), which has received much attention as an approach to conceptualizing and measuring cognitive style (Shalley, Zhou & Oldham, 2004) and has influenced research in a wide range of fields including entrepreneurship, leadership, and team dynamics (Stum, 2009). Adaptation-Innovation Theory posits that individuals differ greatly in the way they make decisions, solve problems, and interpret change (Tullett & Davies, 1997). Such differences in cognitive style develop early in life and determine how an individual deals with all stages of the problem-solving process, including the view of the nature of the problem, the scope of possible solutions, and the implementation of the chosen solutions (Kirton, 1989).

Professors Gianluca Carnabuci and Eric Quintane investigated how and when people build networks that allow them to perform at their best. To this end, they conducted a longitudinal, or time-extended, study experiment within a business unit of a large semiconductor company, tracking the network and performance of each employee for two and a half years.

They found that most employees formed relationships that naturally aligned with their cognitive style, defined as an employee's preferred way of processing information and solving problems. For example, employees who value diversity and creativity build "connective relationships" by branching out and coming together across different groups and departments in the organization.

Why? Because these relationships bring a breadth of thought, perspectives, and ideas that creative employees feel comfortable with. On the other hand, employees who value precision and execution over creativity avoid such connecting relationships and focus instead on strengthening their pre-existing connections within a single group.

Building networks that align with our cognitive style is natural because it makes people feel

Adaptive-Innovative Cognitive Style

Adaptation and Innovation are two ends of a continuum, which have a normal distribution around the theoretical mean (Goldsmith & Kerr, 1991). The descriptions of individuals at the two ends of the continuum are in stark contrast. Adaptors use available information to find solutions that fit within defined frameworks (Kaufmann, 2004). As such, they are more inclined to "do things better" than to "do things differently" (Kirton, 1976: 622). Adaptors' solutions generally fit well with those of others and with the generally accepted way of doing things. However, it is often difficult for adaptors to recognize when existing solutions are no longer effective (Pounds & Bailey, 2001). Furthermore, adaptors tend to analyze problems logically and methodically rather than resorting to free-form idea generation (Basadur, 1995). While this approach helps them solve "problems by moving at a disciplined pace in a predictable direction" (Kirton, 1994: 13), it also makes divergent thinking impossible, reducing their likelihood of generating truly new and creative ideas.

Innovators, on the other hand, process information in a very different way, as their cognitive focus is on finding new ways to conceptualize and frame the problem (Kirton, 1976), rather than on immediate and ready-made solutions. Being less inclined to adapt their ideas to the expectations of others, Innovators typically approach problems from original and unusual perspectives (Singer, 1990), "breaking the usual starting point" for their solution (Kirton & De Ciantis, 1986: 141).

Finally, Innovators find it relatively easy to generate original ideas by recombining seemingly unrelated perspectives and information, although it is quite difficult for them to convert creative ideas into implemented innovations. Conversely, Adaptors come up with fewer and fewer original ideas, but their focus on finding solutions that fit well with the organization's established

ways of doing things helps them in the process of implementing the idea. Such differences in cognitive style describe an individual's preferred way of processing and organizing information, and are thus conceptually distinct from cognitive level or ability (Goldsmith, 1985).

Conclusions and Suggestions

The different cognitive styles of people refer to the way in which this person receives, processes information and how he uses it to understand events and to provide solutions and in decision-making. Social capital is known as the ability and network of relationships of each individual in the group where they share values and resources to do better and more accurately the tasks in society. In other words, it is the ability to take a place in relationships with other people in the group where it functions, whether social or professional. According to studies, people differ in their cognitive style, one of these differences is the way of performance and some are better executors than others who have the ability to make new connections easily. The first, according to the authors, should go a little against the natural trend and increase new connections or networks in order to benefit from new information and connections, while the second group, the one who has new connections as a strong point, should tend to strengthen the execution part and the stronger and deeper connection with the group to which they belong, with which they have to perform actions.

Another important division in the typology of people and their cognitive styles is the innovative style, which naturally suits some creative people better, who have a way of processing information outside the rules, the defined department group and see decision-making in the same line. The second group are adaptive people, who know how to do things better the way they are and not to think about doing new things or doing them differently. Both groups have their advantages and disadvantages, the first group's disadvantage is that they do not find it easy to translate innovative ideas into operational or executive plans, so they lack concreteness in their decision-making. Also, the second group has a deficiency or organizational myopia when it comes to understanding when a certain method is no longer working or when it would be better to change the way of solving problems or performing with another more innovative and efficient idea.

In conclusion, both of these groups must create networks and social capital by consciously involving themselves with the other group different from them, in order to strengthen their weak points and increase the possibility of reducing errors in decision-making and increasing their performance which always works as a consequence or within a group, be it an informal group, department, factory or other.

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